

Description of a new species of Pyralid moth from French Guiana (Lepidoptera, Phycitinae).

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- **Abstract.** A Phycitinae species new to Science is described from French Guiana, Maroni area.
- **Résumé. Description d'une espèce nouvelle de Pyrale de la Guyane (Lepidoptera, Pyraloidea).** Une espèce de Phycitinae nouvelle est décrite de Guyane française, de la région du Maroni.
- **Key-words.** Pyraloidea, Pyralidae, Phycitini, Neotropical area, new species, French Guiana, Guiana Shield, biodiversity, systematics.
- **Mots-clefs.** Pyraloidea, Pyralidae, Phycitini, région néotropicale, espèce nouvelle, Guyane française, bouclier des Guyanes, biodiversité, systématique.

Introduction

A careful and exhaustive review of the Guianese Phycitini within the French national collections revealed some scarce or new species, amongst which the latter is worth publishing before the achievement of a more global work. This adds one species to the presumably well underestimated Pyralidae fauna from the Amazon basin and Guiana Shield.

The present article is based on historical material from the general collection at the MNHN. Literary sources completed the study of the abovementioned collection. Due to the scarcity of primary sources describing new taxa from French Guiana, the author also examined secondary sources such as HEINRICH, 1956, as well as other articles related to the Northern South American area, including Central America and the Caribbean (SHAFFER, 1976; NEUNZIG, 2003; NEUNZIG & DOW, 1993; NEUNZIG & SOLIS, 2002a, 2002b, 2004), the websites *GlobIz* and *Moth Photographers Group* as well as the global work by LERAUT (2021).

Conventions and abbreviations

MNHN : Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris

GL : Guillaume Leraut

prep. : genitalia preparation (slides)

rec. : collector

coll. : collection

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Material and methods

All insects have been preserved within the MNHN general collection (former L. & J. de Joannis coll.), along with other Neotropical material. Genitalia slides have been prepared using a traditional process and preserved in a balm (Euparal brand). Genitalia slides have been deposited in the G. Leraut slides collection, MNHN (former Entomology Laboratory).

Map 1. Map of French Guiana and collection site.

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Illustrations are from the author. Genitalia pictures have been taken on the photography equipment of the MNHN (the author sincerely thanks M. Antoine Mantilleri for authorisation).

Results

Genus *Euzophera* ZELLER, 1867: 456.

Type species. *Myelois cinerosella* ZELLER, 1839: 176. By subsequent designation.

Euzophera joannisorum n. sp.

Derivatio nominis. Dedicated to L. & J. de Joannis, eminent French entomologists of the beginning of the 20th Century and who collected this species.

Holotype. 1 ♂, Saint-Laurent-du-Maroni (no date, coll. L. & J. de Joannis, MNHN), prep. GL n°987.

Paratype. 1 ♀, same locality, prep. GL n°1028.

Diagnosis. Habitus. Wingspan 14-16 mm. Habitus globally quite similar to this of various *Euzophera* species, like *E. semifuneralis* (Walker). Forewings moderately narrow, leather brown with a dusky or coffee brown patch in the costal two thirds of the medial area. Two ante- and post-medial paler stripes delimit this area. Hindwings pale brownish with brown veins. Thorax and body leather brown, fore part of the thorax dusky, testaceous; head dark brown, as well as maxillary and labial palpi and antennae. Antennae thin, filiform; maxillary palpi short, thin; labial palpi thin, upturned, short. - Genitalia. Male genitalia like other *Euzophera* species, valvae moderately short, spatuliform, rounded, uncus rounded, saccus U-shaped, gnathos with a long spike. Aedeagus short, stocky, with a dense concentration of thin spines clustered in two groups. Female genitalia closer to those of *E. ostricolorella* and also *E. nigricantella* Ragonot, papillae anales short, apophyses (anterior and posterior) long, thin, ostium bursae U-shaped, hardly sclerotized, ductus bursae short, corpus bursae globally pyriform, uneven, the proximal part bloated, sclerotized and with tiny spines, the distal part hemispherical.

Observation. This species has a typical *Euzophera* ornamentation. Using the key of HEINRICH (1956) it takes place in the *semifuneralis* species group, but differs significantly from all species known in South America. Most of them remain only known from the Nearctic ecozone.

Figures 1-4. *Euzophera joannisorum* n. sp. 1 – Holotype, male, St. Laurent-du-Maroni; 2 – Labels of the holotype; 3 – Paratype, female, same locality; 4 – Labels of the paratype.

Figures 5-7. *Euzophera joannisorum* n. sp. 5 – Holotype, male, genitalia; 6 – Holotype, male, genitalia : aedeagus; 7 – Paratype, female, genitalia.

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